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Supplement to the checklist of Macromycetes (Fungi) from the village of Wyskok in the Masurian Lakeland, NE Poland

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6973311>

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Abstract: In 2017-2021, a further 22 new species of Macromycetes were recorded in the village of Wyskok in the Masurian Lakeland and its surroundings additional, including Polish red-listed *Fistulina hepatica* (rare) and *Stropharia albonitens* (vulnerable). The updated checklist of macromycetes from Wyskok now contains 347 species. The increasing abundance of the thermophilic species *Amanita strobiliformis* is supposed to be attributed to climate warming.

Key words: Oświn Lake, biodiversity, climate warming.

INTRODUCTION

The diversity of fungi in the vicinity of the village of Wyskok by Lake Oświn was earlier documented with 325 species (HOFFEINS *et al.* 2017). Here we add 22 new species identified from this area. Making a total 347 species of macrofungi from there.

The Material and Methods are described in HOFFEINS *et al.* (2017). The current names and classification were checked with the Mycobank database. All species listed below were collected on 1-15 September 2018-2021, except for *Entoloma clypeatum* collected on 15 June 2019.

The abbreviations for Polish red list of fungi (WOJEWODA & ŁAWRYNOWICZ 2006) are as follows: **Ex** – extinct or lost, **E** – endangered, **V** – vulnerable, **R** – rare, **I** – indetermined threat.

RESULTS

New records of macromycetes from Wyskok

Ascomycota
Pezizomycetes
Pezizales
Helotiales
Helotiaceae

Phaeohelotium monticola (BERK) DENNIS (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. *Phaeohelotium monticola* (BERK) DENNIS, mixed forest, 2018.
Ryc. 1. *Phaeohelotium monticola* (BERK) DENNIS, las mieszany, 2018.

Agaricales
Agaricaceae

Cystoderma jasonis (COOKE & MASSEE) HARMAJA

Macrolepiota rhacodes (VITTAD.) SINGER (Fig. 2)

Lepiota cristata (BOLTON) P. KUMM.

Cortinariaceae

Cortinarius salor FR. (Fig. 3)

Entolomataceae

Clitopilus prunulus (SCOP.) P. KUMM.

Entoloma clypeatum (L.) P. KUMM. (Fig. 4)

Fig. 2. *Macrolepiota rhacodes* (VITTAD.) SINGER, spruce forest, 2021.

Ryc. 2. *Macrolepiota rhacodes* (VITTAD.) SINGER, las świerkowy, 2021.

Fig. 3. *Cortinarius salor* Fr., conifer forest, 2021.

Ryc. 3. *Cortinarius salor* Fr., las iglasty, 2021.

Fig. 4. *Entoloma clypeatum* (L.) P. KUMM., orchard, June 2019.

Ryc. 4. *Entoloma clypeatum* (L.) P. KUMM., sad, czerwiec 2019.

Fig. 5. *Fistulina hepatica* (SCHAEFF.) WITH., on oak, 2021.

Ryc. 5. *Fistulina hepatica* (SCHAEFF.) WITH., na dębie, 2021.

Fistulinaceae

Fistulina hepatica (SCHAEFF.) WITH. (R) (Fig. 5)

Inocybaceae

Inocybe cincinnata (FR.) QUÉL. (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6. *Inocybe cincinnata* (FR.) QUÉL, mixed forest, 2021.

Ryc. 6. *Inocybe cincinnata* (FR.) QUÉL, las mieszany, 2021.

Mycenaceae

Panellus mitis (PERS.) SINGER

Physalacriaceae

Armillaria ostoyae (ROMAGN.) HERINK

Coprinellus truncorum (SCOP.) REDHEAD, VILGALYS & MONCALVO

Flammulina velutipes (CURTIS) SINGER (Fig. 7)

Psathyrella marcescibilis (BRITZELM.) SINGER

Strophariaceae

Galerina marginata (BATSCH) KÜHNER

Stropharia albonitens (FR.) (V)

Tricholomataceae

Lepista irina (FR.) H.E. BIGELOW

Fig. 7. *Flammulina velutipes* (CURTIS) SINGER, on oak, 2018.
Ryc. 7. *Flammulina velutipes* (CURTIS) SINGER, na dębie, 2018.

Auriculariales
Auriculariaceae

Auricularia auricula-judae (BULL.) QUÉL (Fig. 8)

Fig. 8. *Auricularia auricula-judae* (BULL.) QUÉL, on *Sambucus*, 2021.
Ryc. 8. *Auricularia auricula-judae* (BULL.) QUÉL, na *Sambucus*, 2021.

Gomphales
Gomphaceae

Ramaria flaccida (FR.) BOURDO

Hymenochaetales
Hymenochaetaceae

Phellinidium ferrugineofuscum (P. KARST.) FIASSON & NIEMELÄ (Fig. 9)

Fig. 9. *Phellinidium ferrugineofuscum* (P. KARST.) FIASSON & NIEMELÄ, on birch, 2021.

Ryc. 9. *Phellinidium ferrugineofuscum* (P. KARST.) FIASSON & NIEMELÄ, na brzozie, 2021.

Polyporales
Dacryobolaceae

Amaropostia stiptica (PERS.) B.K. CUI, L.L. SHEN & Y.C. DAI

Russulales
Russulaceae

Lactarius pubescens FR.

REMARKS

Within the enclosed yard of our cottage two species – *Lepiota cristata* and *Clitopilus prunulus* have been present over a great many years. They were recorded in a separate (unpublished) list of „yard“ species, among others, but we overlooked them in our previous checklist (HOFFEINS *et al.* 2017).

We would like to add some comments of general interest regarding the increasing abundance of two species – *Amanita strobiliformis* and *Macrolepiota procera* in the vicinity of Wyskok. *A. strobiliformis* first appeared in mid-September 2006 (Fig. 10), when we found a single specimen growing outside our cottage under a lime tree (*Tilia*). In subsequent years, the mycelium spread into the orchard and along the wayside up into a grove with *Betula*; by 2021 had expanded to cover an area of around 500 m². The numbers of *A. strobiliformis* are increasing yearly, reaching a peak mainly in July and August. The second species, *Macrolepiota procera*, is a common fungus in the Masurian Lakeland that has been collected at several localities in the vicinity of Wyskok (Figs. 11, 12). With each year in the period under consideration, *Macrolepiota procera* has been appearing in ever larger clusters, even when the soil humidity has been quite low.

Amanita strobiliformis prefers warm temperatures for initiating fructification. Such thermal conditions currently appear to be more and more stable in early autumn, even in the north-eastern region of Poland (personal observation). We expect additional thermophilic species in the near future as a result of climate warming.

Figs. 10–11. Thermophilic *Amanita strobiliformis* (PAULET ex VITTAD.) BERTILL, near a lime tree, 2006 (Fig. 10) and *Macrolepiota procera* (SCOP.) SINGER, in a meadow near a copse with aspen *Populus tremula* trees, 2020 (Fig. 11). oak, 2018.

Ryc. 10–11. Ciepłolubna *Amanita strobiliformis* (PAULET ex VITTAD.) BERTILL, koło lipy, 2006 (Ryc. 10) oraz *Macrolepiota procera* (SCOP.) SINGER, łąka przy zagajniku z osikami, 2020 (Ryc. 11).

Fig. 12. *Macrolepiota procera* (SCOP.) SINGER, the first author with a giant specimen, 2020.

Ryc. 12. *Macrolepiota procera* (SCOP.) SINGER, gigantyczny okaz z pierwszym autorem, 2020.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are deeply grateful to Dr Marek Halama of Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław, for critical comments on the early draft of the manuscript.

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STRESZCZENIE

Uzupełnienie wykazu grzybów wielkoowocnikowych (Fungi: Macromycetes) wsi Wyskok na Pojezierzu Mazurskim

W latach 2017-2021 w najbliższej okolicy wsi Wyskok na Pojezierzu Mazurskim stwierdzono kolejne 22 gatunki, których nie było w poprzednim wykazie grzybów wielkoowocnikowych z tej miejscowości (HOFFEINS *et al.* 2017). Wśród nich, dwa są umieszczone na polskiej czerwonej liście – *Fistulina hepatica* (rzadki) i *Stropharia albonitens* (narażony na wyginięcie). Uzupełniona lista macromycetes wykazanych z Wysokoku obejmuje zatem 347 gatunków. Rosnąca z roku na rok liczebność ciepłolubnego *Amanita strobiliformis* na Pojezierzu Mazurskim świadczy o ocieplaniu się klimatu także w tej części Polski.

Accepted: 15 June 2022; published: 8 August 2022

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